

1 **Effect of seawater on the biomass composition of Spirulina**
2 **produced using seawater at a pilot-scale**

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16 **Abstract**

17 The microalga *Arthrospira platensis* BEA 005B was produced in 11.4 m³ raceway
18 photobioreactors and a culture medium based on commercial fertilisers and either
19 freshwater or seawater. The biomass productivity of the reactors operated at a fixed
20 dilution rate of 0.3 day⁻¹ decreased from 22.9 g·m⁻²·day⁻¹ when operated using freshwater
21 to 16.3 g·m⁻²·day⁻¹ when the biomass was produced using seawater. The protein content
22 of the biomass produced in seawater was lower; however, the content of essential amino
23 acids including valine, leucine and isoleucine was higher. Seawater also triggered the
24 production of carotenoids and altered the synthesis and accumulation of fatty acids. For
25 example, the biomass produced using seawater showed a 319 and 210% higher content
26 of oleic and eicosenoic acid, respectively. Results demonstrated that it is possible to
27 produce the selected microalga using seawater after an adaptation period and that the
28 composition of the produced biomass is suitable for food applications.

29

30 **Keywords:** Spirulina, vegan protein, microalgae, novel foods, fatty acids, volatile
31 compounds.

32 Introduction

33 Cyanobacteria or blue-green algae are a group of photosynthetic microorganisms that
34 are related to bacteria but are generally referred to as “microalgae”. Their capacity to
35 transform carbon dioxide into valuable organic compounds, using sunlight, led to an
36 increased interest in microalgal biotechnology. The relevance and interest in microalgal
37 biotechnology has increased significantly during the last decade, with microalgae finding
38 diverse applications particularly in the realm of food production.

39 The most well-known cyanobacteria are *Arthrospira platensis* and *Arthrospira maxima*,
40 commercialised as Spirulina. The worlds’ most extensively cultivated microalga is
41 Spirulina, representing over 30% of the total biomass production [1]. Spirulina is
42 especially interesting for the food industry because of its high protein content, which is
43 around 60% on a dry weigh basis [2]. Moreover, other health-promoting compounds such
44 as minerals (e.g. iron, magnesium), vitamins (e.g. vitamin A, vitamin E), carotenoids, and
45 phycobiliproteins (e.g. phycocyanin) are present in Spirulina [3]. For these reasons,
46 Spirulina is today being used as food as a source of blue/green pigments and as a source
47 of protein, especially sold as a food supplement.

48 Microalgae cannot be harvested from the ocean as seaweed and instead, they are
49 cultivated using photobioreactors inland. The most common photobioreactors for
50 producing microalgae are raceways, which are easy to operate and scale-up and have
51 a low construction cost [4]. The production of 1 kg of microalgal biomass requires
52 approximately 1 m³ of process water [5] and there is an increasing interest in reducing
53 the freshwater requirements of microalgae production. Seawater represents around
54 97.5% of all water on the planet [6] and its use should be considered when possible. It
55 is known that the production of Spirulina using seawater is feasible. Indeed, the company
56 Cyanotech Corporation (Kailua-Kona, HI, US) is commercialising Hawaiian Spirulina[®],
57 which is produced using ocean water. However, not all the different strains adapt to the
58 high salinity of seawater. Moreover, little is known about the effect of salt on the

59 biochemical composition of the biomass. A recent study confirmed that the use of
60 seawater results in a reduced protein content and an increased accumulation of
61 carbohydrates [7]. Similar results were observed in a previous study [8]. However, the
62 effect of seawater on the quality of the proteins and on the content of other valuable
63 molecules such as fatty acids and carotenoids is unknown.

64 The first aim of this study was to assess the potential of producing *A. platensis* BEA 005B
65 using seawater instead of freshwater. Minimising the environmental impact of industrial
66 practices is urgent. Moreover, a second aim of this work was to identify the suitability of
67 the produced biomass for being used as food and to evaluate how seawater affects the
68 biochemical composition of *A. platensis* BEA 005B. An interesting aspect of the present
69 work is that the biomass production was carried out using large pilot-scale raceway
70 reactors located outdoors and following industrial practices.

71

72 **Materials and methods**

73 **Strain selection and photobioreactors used**

74 The strain used in this study was *A. platensis* BEA 005, purchased from the Spanish
75 Bank of Algae. The inocula were produced by means of 100 L bubble columns and then
76 using 1.04 m³ raceway reactors (7.13 m²; 0.12 m culture depth) and a medium previously
77 optimised for the production of *A. platensis* [9]. The culture medium consisted of 0.9 g·L⁻¹
78 ¹ NaNO₃, 0.18 g·L⁻¹ MgSO₄, 0.14 g·L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄, and 0.02 g·L⁻¹ of Karentol[®] Mix Super
79 (Kenogard, Barcelona, Spain), a commercial mixture of micronutrients including boron,
80 copper, iron, manganese, molybdenum, and zinc. All the nutrients used for biomass
81 production were commercial-grade fertilisers. When produced using seawater, the
82 microalga was pre-adapted by gradually increasing the concentration of sea salt in the
83 medium from 0 to 35 g·L⁻¹ during approximately 4 months.

84 Pilot-scale production was carried out using 11.4 m³ raceway reactors (80 m²; 0.13 m
85 culture depth) which were operated 24 h per day at a dilution rate of 0.30 day⁻¹. The
86 channels of the raceway were 40 m long and 1 m wide. Each reactor had a 1 m³ sump
87 where air was continuously injected at a flow of 200 L·min⁻¹. Agitation was done by
88 means of a paddlewheel, which allowed a culture velocity of 0.2 m·s⁻¹. Environmental
89 conditions, namely temperature and solar radiation during biomass production are
90 shown in Figure 1. Overall, the average temperature and solar radiation during the
91 biomass production (spring) were 18.3 ± 1.7 °C and 598.9 ± 75.1 μmol·m⁻²·s⁻¹,
92 respectively. The composition of the media used for pilot-scale production was the same
93 than the one used for producing the inocula. The pH was lowered by on-demand injection
94 of carbon dioxide. Two different types of water were used, freshwater and seawater,
95 which was pumped from the Mediterranean Sea (36°49'40.7"N, 2°24'08.2"W). Both
96 reactors were located inside the same greenhouse and were operated simultaneously;
97 therefore, the biomasses produced using freshwater and seawater were subjected to
98 identical environmental and operational conditions (culture depth and dilution rate). The
99 produced biomasses were harvested by centrifugation, dried using a GEA MM-PSR
100 spray drier (GEA Wesfalia Separator, Oelde, Germany), and stored vacuum-sealed at
101 room temperature (21 ± 1 °C) until further use (approximately 1 month). The outlet
102 effluents were stored in 100 m³ deposits and were further used in other research projects
103 related with irrigation and solar desalination.

104 **Assessment of the performance of the culture**

105 The biomass concentration and the Fv/Fm ratio of the culture were determined as
106 described in a previous work [10]. The concentration of nitrates and phosphates was
107 measured as described elsewhere [11] using a GenesysTM 10S UV spectrophotometer
108 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Madrid, Spain).

109 **Analytical determinations**

110 *Macromolecular composition*

111 The protein, lipid, and ash concentration of the biomass was determined as described in
112 a previous work [10]. The carbohydrate content was determined by difference. The
113 energy content was calculated using the factor provided in EU Regulation 1169/2011
114 where carbohydrates, proteins, fats, and fibres account for 4, 4, 9, and 2 kcal·g⁻¹,
115 respectively.

116 *Estimation of the content of phycobiliproteins*

117 Phycobiliproteins, namely phycocyanin (C_P), allophycocyanin (C_A), and phycoerythrin
118 (C_E) were estimated using a Genesys 10S UV spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher
119 Scientific, Spain) and following a previously described methodology [12]. The content of
120 phycobiliproteins was estimated using the equations:

121 $C_P (g \cdot L^{-1}) = \frac{A_{615} - 0.474 \cdot A_{652}}{5.34}$ Equation 4

122 $C_A (g \cdot L^{-1}) = \frac{A_{652} - 0.208 \cdot A_{615}}{5.09}$ Equation 5

123 $C_E (g \cdot L^{-1}) = \frac{A_{562} - 2.41 \cdot C_P \cdot A_{615} - 0.849 \cdot C_A}{9.62}$ Equation 6

124 where A_{615} , A_{652} , and A_{562} are the optical densities measured at 615, 652, or 562 nm,
125 respectively.

126 *Amino acid profile*

127 The determination of amino acids was done following a previously reported methodology
128 [13] and using a Perkin Elmer Series 200 HPLC (PerkinElmer, MA, USA) and a Perkin
129 Elmer Altus A-10 fluorescence detector (PerkinElmer, MA, USA). Samples were
130 determined in duplicate per natural replicate.

131 *Fatty acid profile*

132 The preparation of fatty acid methyl esters and their determination were done following
133 a previously described method [14] using a MARS 6 Express 40 microwave (CEM
134 Corporation, NC, USA), a Clarus 580 gas chromatograph fitted with a flame ionisation
135 detector and a CP-Sil 88 capillary column (100 m × 0.25 mm, 0.2 µm; Agilent, CA, USA).

136 *Carotenoid profile*

137 Determination of carotenoids was conducted following a method described elsewhere
138 [15]. In the present work, the carotenoids were separated and determined with a
139 Beckman Coulter GOLD HPLC system (CA, USA) equipped with a L-7420 ThermoQuest
140 diode-array detector (CA, USA) and a Merck LiChroCART RP-18 column (Darmstadt,
141 Germany), 5 µm size, 250 × 4 mm. Mobile phase A was ethyl acetate and mobile phase
142 B was acetonitrile and water 9:1 (v/v). The flow rate was 1 mL·min⁻¹. The detection was
143 conducted at 450 nm and the quantification was done using analytical-grade standards.

144 *Mineral content*

145 All the plastic material used in analysis were dipped in 10% HNO₃ for 24 h, thoroughly
146 washed with Milli-Q water, and dried in an oven before use. A weight of 0.5 g of
147 homogenized sample was added to Teflon vessels; then, 5 mL of concentrated HNO₃
148 was added and allowed to be pre-digested for 15 min. Then, samples were digested
149 using the CEM-Xpress microwave accelerated unit at up to 200 °C for 20 min in closed
150 vessels. Digested samples were diluted to 50 mL with ultra-pure deionized water.
151 Certified reference samples, reagent blanks and spiked samples were included in each
152 batch of digestion and treated the same manner. The calibration curve was prepared by
153 using Ca, Zn, Fe, Se, Co, K, Na, P, Mg, V stock solution (Sigma Aldrich) with appropriate
154 dilutions. After that, the samples were aspirated into an Agilent 7900 ICP-MS using the
155 conditions given as supplementary material.

156 *Determination of volatile organic compounds*

157 The volatile organic compounds were extracted by solid phase microextraction as
158 described elsewhere [16]. The relative abundance of volatile organic compounds was
159 determined using a 7820A gas chromatograph (Agilent Technologies, Madrid, Spain)
160 coupled to a 5975 series mass spectrometer (Agilent Technologies, Madrid, Spain). The
161 data were analysed with MSD ChemStation Data Analysis version 5.52 (Agilent
162 Technologies, Madrid, Spain).

163 **Statistical analysis**

164 The data were analysed using one-way analysis of variance and a Fishers' LSD post hoc
165 test ($p < 0.05$) using Statgraphics Centurion v18 (Statgraphics Technologies Inc., VA,
166 US).

167

168 **Results and discussion**

169 **Biomass productivity**

170 The composition of the culture medium can affect the composition of microalgal biomass
171 [10]. Indeed, the main goal of the present work was to assess how the use of seawater
172 instead of freshwater affects the biochemical composition of *A. platensis*. Figure 1A and
173 Figure 1B show the solar radiation that reached the cultures and the temperature inside
174 the greenhouse, respectively. Environmental and operational conditions can also affect
175 the composition of microalgae; for example, high light doses negatively affects the
176 growth of the microalga *Nannochloropsis oceanica* and its production and accumulation
177 of polyunsaturated fatty acids and carotenoids [17]. However, in the present study, the
178 biomass was produced using identical photobioreactors that were operated
179 simultaneously and using the same operational conditions. Moreover, the reactors were
180 located inside the same greenhouse; therefore, the results detailed below were not
181 caused by different environmental or operational conditions, but to a different culture
182 media composition (type of water).

183 Figure 1C shows the biomass concentration inside the photobioreactors operated using
184 freshwater or seawater. Overall, the type of water used had a significant effect on the
185 growth of the microalga. The use of seawater led to a significant decrease ($p<0.05$) in
186 the maximum biomass concentration reached at the end of the batch phase from $0.98 \pm$
187 $0.03 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ (freshwater) to $0.90 \pm 0.03 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ (sea water), respectively. Not only the biomass
188 concentration but also the duration of the batch phase was affected ($p<0.05$). When
189 produced using freshwater, the maximum concentration was reached after 9 days of
190 production; in turn, it took 12 days to reach the maximum concentration when the
191 biomass was produced using seawater. The main reason was a longer adaptation phase
192 in the latter, as the specific growth of the microalga in both media was similar. The
193 biomass productivity of the reactors during the semi-continuous production phase was
194 22.9 ± 1.8 and $16.3 \pm 1.9 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$ for the freshwater and seawater media, respectively
195 ($p<0.05$). A comparable decrease in the biomass productivity of *Arthrospira* strains was
196 reported in previous works [7,8]. The F_v/F_m value is a non-invasive measurement of the
197 status of the photosystem PSII activity and of its response to different biotic and abiotic
198 factors. The use of seawater led to a decrease in the F_v/F_m value, which could suggest
199 that the seawater stressed the microalga. This was expected as despite being gradually
200 adapted to salt, the microalga used is a freshwater strain. The effect of seawater was
201 still very low as the F_v/F_m values were in both cases around 0.5, which is the optimum
202 for most Cyanobacteria [18].

203 **Effect of seawater on the protein and phycobiliprotein content of the biomass**

204 The total protein content of the biomass produced using freshwater and seawater is listed
205 in Table 1. The protein content of *A. platensis* BEA 005B was negatively affected by the
206 use of seawater instead of freshwater ($p<0.05$). This is consistent with a recent study
207 that observed a decrease in the protein content of *A. platensis* LEB 18 from 53.5% when
208 produced using the Zarrouks' medium to 48.4% when produced using seawater
209 supplemented with inorganic nutrients [7]. Similarly, in a different study it was reported

210 that seawater reduced the protein content of *A. platensis* from 71.2% when produced
211 using the Zarrouks' medium to 65-66% when produced in seawater supplemented with
212 nutrients [8]. The reason for this decrease was attributed to a change in the metabolism
213 of algae towards the production and accumulation of low molecular weight carbohydrates
214 instead of proteins as a strategy to maintain the osmotic balance of the medium [19].
215 Similarly, down regulation of genes involved in the synthesis of proteins has been
216 observed in higher plants and seaweed [20]. The amino acid content of the produced
217 biomass is shown in Table 2. The use of seawater instead of freshwater affected not only
218 the amount of proteins but also their amino acid composition ($p < 0.05$). Overall, seawater
219 led to a decrease in the concentration of threonine and lysine ($p < 0.05$). In turn, the
220 concentration of valine, isoleucine, leucine, and phenylalanine was higher in the biomass
221 produced using seawater ($p < 0.05$). It is important to highlight that all the essential amino
222 acids were found in the produced biomass independently of the type of water used,
223 demonstrating the potential use of this microalga for the enrichment of foods lacking
224 essential amino acids.

225 Moreover, the content of phycobiliproteins in the biomass is shown in Table 1.
226 Phycobiliproteins are produced by Cyanobacteria and are a group of water soluble
227 proteins with an associated chromophore that are involved in the process of
228 photosynthesis [21]. Phycobiliproteins are divided into four major groups, which are
229 phycocyanins, phycoerythrins, phycoerythrocyanins, and allophycocyanins; they form
230 the phycobilisome, which together with the two main photosystems form the
231 photosynthetic apparatus of cyanobacteria [21]. Phycobiliproteins are especially
232 interesting in the food industry not only for their bioactive properties but also for their
233 intense colours and their potential use as bioactive pigments [22]. In the present work,
234 the biomass produced using seawater had lower phycocyanin and allophycocyanin
235 contents ($p < 0.05$). Similar results were observed in previous works, who attributed the
236 lower phycocyanin yields to the synthesis of low molecular weight carbohydrates for

237 osmotic protection; the authors of that study also suggested that when produced using
238 seawater, the number of purification steps to obtain phycobiliproteins might be greater
239 [8].

240 **Effect of seawater on the lipid content of the biomass**

241 The total lipid content of the biomass produced using freshwater and seawater is listed
242 in Table 1. Overall, the production of the biomass using seawater led to a slight, but
243 significant, higher lipid content ($p<0.05$). Previous works revealed that an increased
244 salinity did not affected significantly the lipid content of *Arthrospira* strains [8]. In turn, a
245 salinity increase led to a higher lipid content in various microalgae including strains of
246 the genus *Scenedesmus* [19] and *Tetraselmis* [23]. It has been suggested that lipids are
247 synthesised and stored when the cells are subjected to stress factors as high-energy
248 storage compounds that are further used as an energy source when the cells are back
249 to optimal conditions.

250 Salt does not only promote the production of lipids but also the composition of the lipid
251 fraction. For example, an increase in salinity increased the content of neutral lipids in the
252 microalga *Chlamydomonas nivalis* as a strategy to increase the rigidity of the cell
253 membrane and avoid an excessive flux of Na^+ and Cl^- into the microalgal cells [24]. The
254 most relevant microalgal lipids for the food industry are long-chain polyunsaturated fatty
255 acids such arachidonic acid (AA, C20:4), eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA, C20:5), and
256 docosahexaenoic acid (DHA, C22:6). They are currently being commercialised for food
257 (and feed) applications. The effect of the water type used for biomass production on the
258 fatty acid composition of the biomass is shown in Table 3. Overall, the type of water used
259 to produce the *Spirulina* affected the fatty acid composition of the biomass ($p<0.05$). The
260 total content of fatty acid methyl esters in the *Spirulina* produced using seawater and
261 freshwater was 3354.3 and 3023.1 $\text{mg}\cdot 100\text{ g}^{-1}$, respectively. The use of seawater
262 triggered the production of hexanal and pentadecanoic, palmitic, stearic, elaidic, oleic,
263 arachidic, and lignoceric acids ($p<0.05$). In turn, the synthesis of caproic, myristic,

264 palmitoleic, linoleic, γ -linoleic, arachidonic, and nervonic acids was diminished when the
265 biomass was produced using seawater ($p < 0.05$). Some fatty acid methyl esters were not
266 detected in the biomass produced using freshwater namely succinic acid and myristoleic
267 acid; in turn, linoleic acid, behenic acid, and docosahexaenoic acid were not
268 synthesised (not detected) in the biomass produced using seawater. Previous works
269 observed that different temperatures and nitrate concentrations could affect the fatty acid
270 composition of *Spirulina* [25]. In our work, both photobioreactors were identical and
271 located inside the same greenhouse; therefore, it is unlikely that the observed differences
272 were caused by the environmental conditions. The fatty acid composition of *Spirulina*
273 has been shown to be strain-dependent; for example, a previous study reported that the
274 linoleic and γ -linolenic acid concentration of 35 different *Arthrospira* strains varied from
275 13.1-31.5 and 12.9-29.4% of total fatty acids, respectively [26]. In this work, the observed
276 differences were attributed to the type of water used. The most marked effects of using
277 seawater were a 319 and 210% increase in the synthesis of oleic acid and 11-eicosenoic
278 acid, respectively. The great increase in the synthesis and accumulation of oleic acid is
279 especially interesting for food applications because its consumption has been linked to
280 lower total cholesterol and LDL-cholesterol levels, an improved glycaemic profile, and
281 the prevention of some types of cancer [27]. Moreover, a high oleic acid content could
282 improve the stability of the biomass against lipid oxidation that could alter the
283 organoleptic and sensorial attributes of the product [28]. This is, to the best of the authors'
284 knowledge, the first time that such a significant increase in the oleic content of a
285 microalga was observed.

286 Carotenoids are lipophilic antioxidant pigments which can be divided into carotenes
287 (hydrocarbons lacking oxygen) and xanthophylls (oxygenated molecules) and are
288 gaining increased interest in the food industry [29]. Microalgal carotenoids such as β -
289 carotene derived from *Dunaliella salina* and astaxanthin derived from *Haematococcus*
290 *pluvialis* are currently being commercialised and are two of the most recent examples of

291 microalgae-based processes that achieved commercial success. Both microalgae
292 produce and accumulate these highly antioxidant carotenoids as a response to a stress
293 factor. The total carotenoid content of the produced biomass, assessed
294 spectrophotometrically, is shown in Table 1. Results suggested that the total carotenoid
295 content of the biomass was not affected by the type of water used. The carotenoid profile
296 of the biomass is provided as supplementary material. When assessed using
297 chromatographic techniques, the seawater led to a higher content of lutein, zeaxanthin,
298 and lycopene ($p < 0.05$). In turn, the β -carotene concentration of the biomass was not
299 affected. Results are consistent with those reported in a previous work where seawater
300 did not affect the concentration of β -carotene in a salinity-adapted *A. platensis* strain [8].
301 An increased salinity also triggered the production and accumulation of carotenoids in a
302 microalga from the genus *Scenedesmus* [30]. Moreover, as mentioned above, other
303 microalgae produce and accumulate carotenoids as a response to a stress factors (*D.*
304 *salina* or *H. pluvialis*). In the present work, it is likely that the higher salinity of the
305 seawater-based medium triggered the production of carotenoids. These results are in
306 line with the lower productivity and F_v/F_m values in the cultures produced using seawater,
307 which suggested that the microalgal cells were being exposed to some kind of stress.
308 The main carotenoids identified in the biomass were β -carotene and zeaxanthin, which
309 is in line with previous works where carotenoids were extracted from commercial
310 *Spirulina* [31]. Overall, results suggested that despite affecting the biomass and protein
311 productivity of the process, the use of seawater could be used as a strategy to trigger
312 the production and accumulation of carotenoids. In this study, the extraction of the
313 carotenoids was done using acetonitrile; the goal was just to analyse the carotenoid
314 content of the biomass. At the industrial level, where the goal is to obtain carotenoid-rich
315 extracts, the use of more sustainable solvents such as supercritical carbon dioxide, ionic
316 liquids, or natural deep eutectic solvents should be targeted [32].

317 **Mineral content of *A. platensis* produced using freshwater or seawater**

318 The ash content of the biomass produced using freshwater and seawater is listed in
319 Table 1. Overall, the production of the biomass using seawater instead of freshwater led
320 to an increase in the total ash content ($p<0.05$). The mineral content of *A. platensis* was
321 highly influenced by the type of water used ($p<0.05$). The mineral content of the biomass
322 is listed in Table 4. The use of seawater had a significant effect on the mineral content
323 of the biomass ($p<0.05$), especially the concentration of Na, Ca, and Se was significantly
324 increased ($p<0.05$). In turn, lower concentrations of P and Fe were found in the seawater-
325 produced spirulina ($p<0.05$). Overall, the content of some minerals was higher than that
326 reported in previous works [33] but results were comparable to those available at the
327 USDA food database (<https://fdc.nal.usda.gov/>) for powdered Spirulina products
328 commercialised in the US (except for Na). The content of Na was especially high in both
329 biomasses; this was attributed to the content of sodium bicarbonate and to the sodium
330 chloride in seawater. As sodium intake is a major determinant of blood pressure, future
331 works will assess the effect of rinsing the biomass with freshwater before drying on the
332 content of minerals. No heavy metals (Hg, Pt, Ni, Cd, or Pb) were detected in either
333 biomasses.

334 **Characterisation of the volatile organic compounds in the biomass of *A. platensis*** 335 **produced using freshwater or seawater**

336 One of the main challenges of introducing microalgal biomass into Western diets is their
337 strong “marine” odour and flavour [34], limiting their use to marine culinary preparations
338 or their use at low concentrations as a colouring ingredient or as a marketing strategy.
339 However, the number of studies assessing the content of volatile compounds in Spirulina
340 is very limited [16,35]. Table 5 lists the relative abundance of volatile compounds in the
341 biomass produced using either freshwater or seawater. Overall, 28 volatile compounds
342 were detected in the two strains studied. A recent study revealed a high content of volatile
343 organic compounds in the biomass of *A. platensis* BEA 005B [16]. In that study, 95
344 different volatile compounds were identified in *A. platensis* biomass. The lower number

345 of compounds identified in this work can be attributed to the different production and
346 processing strategies followed in both studies. In the cited work [16], the *Spirulina* was
347 produced in controlled closed photobioreactors and the biomass was dried by
348 lyophilisation. In the present study, the biomass was produced using a much larger open
349 photobioreactor and the biomass was dried by spray drying. The present work is more
350 representative of industrial practices. Future studies should assess the effect of the
351 photobioreactor design as well as the effect of harvesting, processing, and drying on the
352 volatile organic compounds content of microalgae. Overall, the abundance of volatile
353 compounds was comparable in both samples; however, some minor differences were
354 observed. For example, the use of seawater led to a lower relative abundance of nonane
355 and a higher content of 3-decanone and heptadecane ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore,
356 trochloroacetic acid, 2-octanone, and hexadecane were only identified in the biomass
357 produced using freshwater whereas hexanal, butylfuran, and styrene were only present
358 when the biomass was produced using seawater. Therefore, results demonstrated an
359 effect of seawater on the volatile organic content of the biomass.

360

361 **Conclusions**

362 This work evaluated the effect of using seawater instead of freshwater for the production
363 of food-grade *A. platensis*. The use of seawater led to a decreased biomass productivity;
364 however, the results demonstrated the possibility of producing *A. platensis* BEA 005B
365 using seawater after an acclimation stage. This strategy could be used to save large
366 volumes of freshwater needed for producing microalgae. The composition of the
367 biomasses was significantly affected by the type of water used during their production.
368 The changes in the composition were attributed to an effort of the cells to maintain the
369 osmotic balance of the medium. The synthesis of certain valuable compounds such as
370 oleic acid or zeaxanthin was triggered in the biomass produced using seawater. These
371 are valuable compounds for food applications highlighting the potential of the biomass

372 for being used in the functional foods market. The results also suggested that not only
373 the type of water used but also the photobioreactor design and the harvesting and
374 processing strategies followed during the biomass production might affect the volatile
375 organic compounds content of microalgae. Future studies should assess the effect of
376 biomass production and processing on the biochemical composition and organoleptic
377 attributes of microalgae. The latter are generally overlooked but are key to promote the
378 consumption of Spirulina.

379

380 **Supplementary data**

381 E-supplementary data of this document can be found in the online version of the paper.

382

383 **Data availability**

384 Data related with the biomass production is accessible at the SABANA Data Center
385 (<http://www2.ual.es/sabana/data-center-2/>). The rest of the data will be made available
386 on request.

387

388 **CRedit author statement**

389 **S. Villaró**: Investigation, Formal Analysis, Writing – Original Draft; **M. García-Vaquero**:
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393

394 **Declaration of interests**

395 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
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410 **References**

- 411 [1] Costa JAV, Freitas BCB, Rosa GM, Moraes L, Morais MG, Mitchell BG.
412 Operational and economic aspects of Spirulina-based biorefinery. *Bioresour*
413 *Technol* 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2019.121946>.
- 414 [2] Lafarga T, Sánchez-Zurano A, Villaró S, Morillas-España A, Acien G. Industrial
415 production of spirulina as a protein source for bioactive peptide generation.
416 *Trends Food Sci Technol* 2021;116:176–85.
417 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2021.07.018>.
- 418 [3] Lafarga T, Fernández-Sevilla JM, González-López C, Acien-Fernández FG.
419 Spirulina for the food and functional food industries. *Food Res Int*
420 2020;137:109356. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2020.109356>.
- 421 [4] Barceló-Villalobos M, Guzmán Sánchez JL, Martín Cara I, Sánchez Molina JA,
422 Acien Fernández FG. Analysis of mass transfer capacity in raceway reactors.
423 *Algal Res* 2018;35:91–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.algal.2018.08.017>.
- 424 [5] Murphy CF, Allen DT. Energy-water nexus for mass cultivation of algae. *Environ*
425 *Sci Technol* 2011;45:5681–6.
426 https://doi.org/10.1021/ES200109Z/SUPPL_FILE/ES200109Z_SI_001.PDF.
- 427 [6] Shannon MA, Bohn PW, Elimelech M, Georgiadis JG, Mariñas BJ, Mayes AM.
428 Science and technology for water purification in the coming decades. *Nat* 2008
429 4527185 2008;452:301–10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature06599>.
- 430 [7] Bezerra PQM, Moraes L, Cardoso LG, Druzian JI, Morais MG, Nunes IL, et al.
431 Spirulina sp. LEB 18 cultivation in seawater and reduced nutrients: Bioprocess
432 strategy for increasing carbohydrates in biomass. *Bioresour Technol*
433 2020;316:123883. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2020.123883>.
- 434 [8] Mary Leema JT, Kirubakaran R, Vinithkumar NV, Dheen PS, Karthikayulu S.

- 435 High value pigment production from *Arthrospira* (*Spirulina*) *platensis* cultured in
436 seawater. *Bioresour Technol* 2010;101:9221–7.
437 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2010.06.120>.
- 438 [9] Gómez C, Guzmán-Carrasco A, Lafarga T, Ación-Fernández FG.
439 OPTIMIZATION OF A NEW CULTURE MEDIUM FOR THE LARGE-SCALE
440 PRODUCTION OF PROTEIN-RICH *ARTHROSPIRA PLATENSIS* (
441 *OSCILLATORIALES, CYANOPHYCEAE*). *J Phycol* 2021;57:636–44.
442 <https://doi.org/10.1111/jpy.13111>.
- 443 [10] Villaró S, Sánchez-Zurano A, Ciardi M, Alarcón FJ, Clagnan E, Adani F, et al.
444 Production of microalgae using pilot-scale thin-layer cascade photobioreactors:
445 Effect of water type on biomass composition. *Biomass and Bioenergy*
446 2022;163:106534. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BIOMBIOE.2022.106534>.
- 447 [11] Ciardi M, Gómez-Serrano C, Morales-Amaral M del M, Ación G, Lafarga T,
448 Fernández-Sevilla JM. Optimisation of *Scenedesmus almeriensis* production
449 using pig slurry as the sole nutrient source. *Algal Res* 2022;61:102580.
450 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.algal.2021.102580>.
- 451 [12] Rodrigues RDP, de Lima PF, Santiago-Aguiar RS de, Rocha MVP. Evaluation of
452 protic ionic liquids as potential solvents for the heating extraction of
453 phycobiliproteins from *Spirulina* (*Arthrospira*) *platensis*. *Algal Res*
454 2019;38:101391. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ALGAL.2018.101391>.
- 455 [13] Bongiorno T, Foglio L, Proietti L, Vasconi M, Lopez A, Pizzera A, et al.
456 Microalgae from Biorefinery as Potential Protein Source for Siberian Sturgeon
457 (*A. baerii*) Aquafeed. *Sustainability* 2020;12:8779.
458 <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12218779>.
- 459 [14] Garcia-Vaquero M, Rajauria G, Miranda M, Sweeney T, Lopez-Alonso M,
460 O'Doherty J. Seasonal Variation of the Proximate Composition, Mineral Content,

- 461 Fatty Acid Profiles and Other Phytochemical Constituents of Selected Brown
462 Macroalgae. *Mar Drugs* 2021, Vol 19, Page 204 2021;19:204.
463 <https://doi.org/10.3390/MD19040204>.
- 464 [15] Fuentes JL, Montero Z, Cuaresma M, Ruiz-Domínguez MC, Mogedas B, Nores
465 IG, et al. Outdoor large-scale cultivation of the acidophilic microalga *Coccomyxa*
466 *onubensis* in a vertical close photobioreactor for lutein production. *Processes*
467 2020. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr8030324>.
- 468 [16] Moran L, Bou G, Aldai N, Ciardi M, Morillas-España A, Sánchez-Zurano A, et al.
469 Characterisation of the volatile profile of microalgae and cyanobacteria using
470 solid-phase microextraction followed by gas chromatography coupled to mass
471 spectrometry. *Sci Rep* 2022;12:3661. [https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-07677-4)
472 [07677-4](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-07677-4).
- 473 [17] Ljubic A, Jacobsen C, Holdt SL, Jakobsen J. Microalgae *Nannochloropsis*
474 *oceanica* as a future new natural source of vitamin D3. *Food Chem*
475 2020;320:126627. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODCHEM.2020.126627>.
- 476 [18] Morillas-España A, Sánchez-Zurano A, Gómez-Serrano C, Ciardi M, Ación G,
477 Clagnan E, et al. Potential of the cyanobacteria *Anabaena* sp. and
478 *Dolichospermum* sp. for being produced using wastewater or pig slurry:
479 Validation using pilot-scale raceway reactors. *Algal Res* 2021;60:102517.
480 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.algal.2021.102517>.
- 481 [19] Pancha I, Chokshi K, Maurya R, Trivedi K, Patidar SK, Ghosh A, et al. Salinity
482 induced oxidative stress enhanced biofuel production potential of microalgae
483 *Scenedesmus* sp. *CCNM 1077*. *Bioresour Technol* 2015;189:341–8.
484 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BIORTECH.2015.04.017>.
- 485 [20] Dittami SM, Gravot A, Renault D, Goulitquer S, Eggert A, Bouchereau A, et al.
486 Integrative analysis of metabolite and transcript abundance during the short-term

487 response to saline and oxidative stress in the brown alga *Ectocarpus siliculosus*.
488 *Plant Cell Environ* 2011;34:629–42. [https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1365-](https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1365-3040.2010.02268.X)
489 [3040.2010.02268.X](https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1365-3040.2010.02268.X).

490 [21] Pagels F, Guedes AC, Amaro HM, Kijjoo A, Vasconcelos V. Phycobiliproteins
491 from cyanobacteria: Chemistry and biotechnological applications. *Biotechnol Adv*
492 2019;37:422–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biotechadv.2019.02.010>.

493 [22] García AB, Longo E, Bermejo R. The application of a phycocyanin extract
494 obtained from *Arthrospira platensis* as a blue natural colorant in beverages. *J*
495 *Appl Phycol* 2021;33:3059–70. [https://doi.org/10.1007/S10811-021-02522-](https://doi.org/10.1007/S10811-021-02522-Z/TABLES/4)
496 [Z/TABLES/4](https://doi.org/10.1007/S10811-021-02522-Z/TABLES/4).

497 [23] Pugkaew W, Meetam M, Yokthongwattana K, Leeratsuwan N, Pokethitiyook P.
498 Effects of salinity changes on growth, photosynthetic activity, biochemical
499 composition, and lipid productivity of marine microalga *Tetraselmis suecica*. *J*
500 *Appl Phycol* 2019;31:969–79. [https://doi.org/10.1007/S10811-018-1619-](https://doi.org/10.1007/S10811-018-1619-7/TABLES/2)
501 [7/TABLES/2](https://doi.org/10.1007/S10811-018-1619-7/TABLES/2).

502 [24] Lu N, Wei D, Jiang XL, Chen F, Yang ST. Regulation of lipid metabolism in the
503 snow alga *Chlamydomonas nivalis* in response to NaCl stress: An integrated
504 analysis by cytomic and lipidomic approaches. *Process Biochem* 2012;47:1163–
505 70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.PROCBIO.2012.04.011>.

506 [25] Colla LM, Bertolin TE, Costa JAV. Fatty Acids Profile of *Spirulina platensis*
507 Grown under Different Temperatures and Nitrogen Concentrations. *Zeitschrift*
508 *Fur Naturforsch - Sect C J Biosci* 2004;59:55–9. [https://doi.org/10.1515/ZNC-](https://doi.org/10.1515/ZNC-2004-1-212/MACHINEREADABLECITATION/RIS)
509 [2004-1-212/MACHINEREADABLECITATION/RIS](https://doi.org/10.1515/ZNC-2004-1-212/MACHINEREADABLECITATION/RIS).

510 [26] Mühling M, Belay A, Whitton BA. Variation in fatty acid composition of
511 *Arthrospira* (*Spirulina*) strains. *J Appl Phycol* 2005 172 2005;17:137–46.
512 <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10811-005-7213-9>.

- 513 [27] Pastor R, Bouzas C, Tur JA. Beneficial effects of dietary supplementation with
514 olive oil, oleic acid, or hydroxytyrosol in metabolic syndrome: Systematic review
515 and meta-analysis. *Free Radic Biol Med* 2021;172:372–85.
516 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FREERADBIOMED.2021.06.017>.
- 517 [28] Talcott ST, Passeretti S, Duncan CE, Gorbet DW. Polyphenolic content and
518 sensory properties of normal and high oleic acid peanuts. *Food Chem*
519 2005;90:379–88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODCHEM.2004.04.011>.
- 520 [29] Santos Assunção L, Quênia Muniz Bezerra P, Stahl Hermes Poletto V, de
521 Oliveira Rios A, Graça Ramos I, Duarte Ferreira Ribeiro C, et al. Combination of
522 carotenoids from Spirulina and PLA/PLGA or PHB: New options to obtain
523 bioactive nanoparticles. *Food Chem* 2021;346:128742.
524 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODCHEM.2020.128742>.
- 525 [30] Aburai N, Sumida D, Abe K. Effect of light level and salinity on the composition
526 and accumulation of free and ester-type carotenoids in the aerial microalga
527 *Scenedesmus* sp. (Chlorophyceae). *Algal Res* 2015;8:30–6.
528 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ALGAL.2015.01.005>.
- 529 [31] Careri M, Furlattini L, Mangia A, Musci M, Anklam E, Theobald A, et al.
530 Supercritical fluid extraction for liquid chromatographic determination of
531 carotenoids in *Spirulina Pacifica* algae: a chemometric approach. *J Chromatogr*
532 *A* 2001;912:61–71. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673\(01\)00545-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673(01)00545-3).
- 533 [32] Yu J, Liu X, Zhang L, Shao P, Wu W, Chen Z, et al. An overview of carotenoid
534 extractions using green solvents assisted by Z-isomerization. *Trends Food Sci*
535 *Technol* 2022;123:145–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TIFS.2022.03.009>.
- 536 [33] Grosshagauer S, Kraemer K, Somoza V. The True Value of Spirulina. *J Agric*
537 *Food Chem* 2020;68:4109–15. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.9b08251>.

- 538 [34] Chacón-Lee TL, González-Mariño GE. Microalgae for “Healthy” Foods-
539 Possibilities and Challenges. *Compr Rev Food Sci Food Saf* 2010.
540 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1541-4337.2010.00132.x>.
- 541 [35] Van Durme J, Goiris K, De Winne A, De Cooman L, Muylaert K. Evaluation of
542 the volatile composition and sensory properties of five species of microalgae. *J*
543 *Agric Food Chem* 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf403112k>.
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546 **Figure legends**

547 **Figure 1. (A) Solar radiation and (B) Temperature during biomass production. (C)**
548 **Biomass concentration and (D) Biomass productivity and chlorophyll**
549 **fluorescence.**

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